

Effect of Rib Geometry on the Buckling Behavior of Composite Isogrid Cylinders

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SUMMARY: Isogrid is a structural concept that utilizes the use of repetitive equilateral pattern of stiffening ribs. The fact that the triangular grids behave entirely as an isotropic material gives rise to the name 'isogrid'. The idea of isogrid is not entirely new; it has been previously introduced in metallic structures which resulted in significant improvement in structural integrity. Recently, Air Force Phillips Laboratory, Lockheed Martin and NASA are conducting extensive research in developing composite isogrid structures for future shuttle constructions. Especially, in the construction of intertank and external fuel tanks, composite isogrid structures will play an important role. Isogrid can effectively carry combined loads because of the arrangement of the ribs. They also permit local skin buckling in large lightweight thin structures without triggering instabilities. In this investigation, both static and buckling analysis have been performed for composite isogrid cylinders using finite element methods (FEM). Two steps were adopted for the development of the finite element models. First, a unit cell representative of the cylindrical structure has been modeled. Secondly, several unit cells have been generated in multiples to form into a complete cylinder. Three different isogrid cylinders have been modeled with three different rib geometry; rectangular, triangular and taper. Axial loads were then applied on the cylinder, and parametric studies were conducted with various rib geometry. Buckling analysis has also been performed for the three categories of isogrid cylinders. Critical failure loads, and various modes of buckling were determined for each of the three cylinders. The local skin buckling phenomenon for cylindrical structure has been studied by analyzing the various failure modes. Details of the finite element analysis are presented in this paper.

KEYWORDS: composite structures, buckling, finite element method (FEM)

INTRODUCTION

The investigation of efficient, lightweight, cost-effective aerospace vehicle is a major goal of the aerospace industry. Structural efficiency is an important aspect of the design of cost-effective aircraft structures and this can be achieved by using isogrid into the main structure of the spacecraft. The selection of lightweight, high-strength materials have been narrowed down to the isogrid structure. A few of the characteristics of isogrid that make this structure attractive to designers are, 1) they behave isotropically, which means that the properties are uniformly distributed throughout the entire framework, and 2) it has the ability to withstand both compression and bending, which are essential criteria for spacecraft design. The isotropic property and effective Poisson's ratio of 1/3, enables the isogrid to be mathematically transformed to an equivalent homogeneous material layer. This transformed expression can be substituted into shell equations to

analyze the overall behavior of isogrid structures. Further optimization of these characteristics are being investigated and the primary focus is now on composite materials. The isogrid-stiffened structures when formed into cylindrical forms become useful for space-craft tankage, interstages and in the skylab crew quarters. It may also function as a protective compartment housing for the operational instruments and a wide range of safety components.

The study of isogrid structures goes back to the late fifties and early sixties. One of the first projects to employ the isogrid structure was the Delta Launch Vehicle project which began in 1959. This design was incorporated into the external skin structure of the booster and was machined from flat 5.27 cm (5/2 in) thick 54ST6 free machining aluminum alloy plate, brake-formed into curved shapes and finally welded into 2.44m (4ft) diameter tank shells. The evaluation of isogrid structures indicated that they possessed advantages that were critical to the improvement of aircraft structures [1]. This reinforced the decision to design the interstage and the fairing for new model Deltas, using isogrid structures. Likewise, one of the earliest analysis was performed using finite element program NASTRAN [2]. The importance of this analysis, was to determine the general instability and theoretical allowable for compression loading. This included axial compression, equivalent axial compression due to bending, as well as offsetting axial tension forces due to internal pressure. The earliest detailed usage of composite material found in this investigation was performed by McDonnell Douglas Astronautics Company in 1972, where three composite cylinders were designed with the isogrid patterns on the external surface of the cylinder [3-4]. Each cylinder experienced one of the mode of buckling behavior of isogrid stiffened structure which was either general - instability buckling, skin buckling or rib crippling.

The first continuous filament isogrid stiffened structure was produced in 1976. Again, compression buckling and dynamic behavior of the structure was tested. One study on a Lockheed C-530 transport aircraft center fuselage using the continuous filament winding structure, showed a weight savings of 20-30 percent over metallic design. As recent as 1992 and 1993, more studies were done on these structures using the COSMOS/M finite element analysis (FEA) program, which was used to determine the buckling load for a composite isogrid flat panel. FEA was also used to verify the feasibility of using acoustic barrier vibration control (ABVC) system with the isogrid structure. As part of very recent works, the effect of stiffness discontinuities and selected structural parameters on the behavior of grid stiffened panels, specifically the effects of both manufacturing introduced stiffness discontinuities and induced damage on grid stiffened panels were performed by Reddy and Rehfield [5-6]. The studies were performed on both isogrid and orthogrid panels.

The literature survey conducted so far does not reveal any studies concerning the effect of rib geometry. Three different rib geometry have therefore, been considered in this investigation. Buckling as well as static compression analyses have been performed on each of these geometry, and a comparison of their failure modes is presented in this paper.

FINITE ELEMENT MODELING

ANSYS [7] finite element code has been used to conduct the present investigation. The isogrid cylinders have been modeled with 8-noded structural solid element, SOLID46. This is a layered version of the 8 noded structural solid which allows up to 100 different material layers and has three degrees of freedom at each node; translations in the nodal x, y and z directions. The three different rib geometry considered in the finite element analysis are shown in Fig. 1. The skin section of the cylinders have been configured with four layers, and their rib sections with 12 layers. The lay up sequence for the skin is $[0^0/45^0/-45^0/90^0]$ while it is $\bar{t}60^0$ for the rib. Carbon/epoxy composites were used as the materials for the isogrid structures, and the properties used were: $E_x = 139.85$ GPa, $E_y = 25.32$ GPa, $G_{xy} = 7.12$ GPa & $\nu_{xy} = 0.32$ [8].

The applied axial compressive load for the three different isogrid cylinders have been computed according to the formulations used in the "Isogrid Design Hand Book", [9]. This value was calculated obtained as 650 MPa according to equation (2) shown below. These equations are based on skin buckling as a primary failure mode. Another set of equations related to rib crippling phenomenon have been ignored for the current analysis. The natural tendency of a thinner part is to be buckled before that of thicker part justifies the use of the selected set of equations. Loading and boundary conditions under axial compression is presented in Fig. 2. The expression for critical load in terms of skin and rib parameters can be written as [9]:

$$N_c = 10.87E \bar{t} \left(\frac{t}{h} \right)^2 \quad (1)$$

$$f_c = \frac{N_c}{\bar{t}} \quad (2)$$

Where, N_c = critical load for skin buckling in compression, N/m

E = Young's Modulus of elasticity, MPa.

t = skin thickness, m

h = height of isogrid triangle, m.

\bar{t} = equivalent skin thickness, m

f_c = allowable compression stress, MPa,

and \bar{t} can be defined by the equations (3) and (4) shown below:

$$\bar{t} = \alpha(t + 1) \quad (3)$$

And
$$\alpha = \frac{bd}{th} \quad (4)$$

Where, b = width of the isogrid rib, m.

d = rib thickness, m.

In our current buckling analysis, eigenvalue buckling analysis has been used to predict the theoretical buckling strength. Eigenvalue analysis requires the stress stiffness to be calculated. Unit loads are usually sufficient. The actual load value need not to be specified. The eigenvalues calculated by the buckling analysis represent buckling load factors. Therefore, if a unit load is specified, the load factors represent the buckling load. In a reduced eigenvalue buckling analysis, all constraints should have zero value. Number of modes needs to be extracted depends on user defined numbers. In the present case five modes are extracted for the buckling analysis.

For the reduced method, the system of equations is first condensed down to those Degrees of Freedoms (DoFs) associated with the master DoFs by Guyan reduction. The set of n master DoFs characterize the natural frequencies in the system. This technique preserves the potential energy of the system but modifies to some extent the kinetic energy. The kinetic energy of the low frequency modes is less sensitive to the condensation than kinetic energy of the high frequency modes. The number of master DoFs selected should usually be at least equal to twice the number of frequencies of interest. This reduced form can be expressed as :

$$[K] \{ \varphi_i \} = \lambda_i [S] \{ \varphi_i \} \quad (5)$$

Where: [K] = Stiffness matrix

[S] = Stress stiffness matrix

λ_i = ith eigenvalue (used to multiply the loads which generated [S])

$\{ \varphi_i \}$ = ith eigenvector of displacements

Using different transformation techniques, equation (5) is converted into standard eigenvalue problem. In this case both sides of equation (5) is pre-multiplied by [S] and then decompose [S] by Cholesky decomposition. Final form of standard eigenvalue equation is shown by equation (6). Eigenvalues are then calculated solving equation (6) with the help of Sturm sequence checks with bisection method.

$$([A] - \lambda [I]) \{ \varphi \} = 0 \quad (6)$$

Where: [A] = Symmetric matrix

[I] = Identity matrix

λ = Eigenvalue of [A], which indicates critical buckling load

$\{ \varphi \}$ = Eigenvector of [A], which gives buckling modes.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Since the axial, radial and interlaminar shear stresses are important for determining the failure mechanisms of isogrid cylinders, distributions of these stresses are analyzed in the present investigation. Both D/L and d/t ratios were kept constant for three different categories so that it was possible to conduct a comparative study between them. The through-thickness distributions of axial, radial and interlaminar shear stresses for three different rib geometry are shown in Figs. 3, 4 and 5. respectively. These distributions are plotted in the locations of maximum stress in each case.

As observed in Fig. 3, axial stress distribution shows a peak of 1250 MPa in case of isogrid cylinders with triangular rib. The maximum stress is seen to occur at the rib-skin interface. The corresponding values for taper and rectangular geometry are respectively 1100 MPa and 940 MPa. It is observed in Fig. 3 that for all three categories, σ_z is maximum at the rib-skin interface. It is also noticed that rectangular geometry experiences the minimum stress while the triangular geometry experiences the highest. The stress distributions observed in Fig. 3 indicate that stress magnitudes increase as one moves from the top of the skin towards the rib-skin interface. At the interface the stresses are compressive for all three categories. It is also noticed that high compressive stresses seem to recover as one approaches from the interface towards the tip of the rib. However, the stresses at the tips are not negligible, and their magnitudes are slightly lower than what have been found at the top of the skin. The transition in stress pattern as seen in Fig. 3 suggest a potential problem of stress concentration. This concentration of stress is due to the abrupt change in geometry as one moves from skin to the rib. The high compressive stresses at the interface are supposed to cause matrix cracking, and also local buckling and kinking of fibers.

The through-thickness distributions of radial stress for three different rib geometry are plotted in Fig. 4. The stress patterns are almost reverse of what was seen in Fig. 3. Here again, the stress transition takes place at the rib-skin interface. It is interesting to note that for rectangular and taper cross-sections, the stresses are always negative while they are positive for the triangular case. It is to be noted here that positive radial stress is considered in the direction of positive radius of the cylinder, that is outward from the center of the cylinder. In the region of the junction between the rib and the skin, the stress magnitudes for both rectangular and taper cross sections are negligible. For the rectangular rib, this stress remains almost unchanged up to the tip of the rib, but it increases rapidly for the taper rib attaining a maximum value of about 3500 MPa. This high value of compressive radial stress near the extremity of the rib is good in one sense that this will nullify any rib-compaction defect derived from the manufacturing process. For the other two categories, the radial stresses at the tip are either minimal or slightly tensile.

A concurrent experimental study of composite isogrid cylinders (not included in this paper) has indicated that there are enough delaminations in the neighborhood of the nodes of the cylinder. These nodes are defined as the intersections of the ribs as they are

wound during manufacturing. In the FEM study, it was intended to look into the cause of such delaminations. It is understood that delamination in a composite laminate can be caused by either interlaminar tensile or interlaminar shear stresses. Interlaminar tensile stress, which is the tensile radial stress, has been discussed in Fig. 4. Now interlaminar shear stress distributions are shown Fig. 5. For all the three categories, interlaminar shear stresses attain their maximum values close to the outer surface of skin. The stress magnitudes decrease as one moves to the inner wall and then to the tip of the ribs. The tips practically experience no shear stresses. High interlaminar shear stress near the outer surface suggests that massive delamination may also occur in a region away from the rib-skin junction. Once delamination sets in, the skin will be more vulnerable to local buckling.

The analysis presented above is the response of the cylinder under quasi-static axial load without considering the buckling effect. As indicated earlier, buckling analysis was also conducted under this investigation. Five modes of buckling were extracted. Isogrid cylinders with triangular rib geometry showed maximum critical value, which was in the range of 836 KN to 924 KN. These values were twice as much as they were found with the rectangular rib geometry. The critical values for taper rib geometry is around 140.8 KN. The higher critical load obtained for triangular rib geometry illustrates the fact that triangular rib geometry will have higher stiffening capabilities than the other two rib-geometry. Deformed shapes for the 5th mode buckling of the three categories of cylinders are shown in Figs. 6 through 8. Out of these three categories, the triangular geometry is found to buckle to the maximum extent. The higher distortion is believed to be due to the higher load taken by the triangular geometry before collapsing. In case of taper geometry, clear separations are observed between the skin and rib sections at multiple places. The multiple delaminations will eventually reduce the load bearing capacity of the cylinder. This explains the fact that the critical buckling load in this case is 1/6th of triangular and 1/3rd of rectangular geometry. Buckling mode of the rectangular geometry is somewhat intermediate between the other two. There are also no visible separation as it was found with taper geometry.

CONCLUSIONS

From buckling analysis it appears that the triangular geometry would be the best among the three sets of rib geometry. However, if we look at the stress distributions, triangular section presents the poorest scenario. Higher stresses with this geometry will trigger failure modes at the rib-skin interface well ahead of the other two geometry. On the other hand, the rectangular geometry offers a balanced view. From stress concentration point of view rectangular geometry has the lowest value, while it has critical buckling load intermediate between the triangular and the taper geometry. In addition to this, rectangular ribs experience the minimum interlaminar stresses at the rib extremities indicating that delamination failure will be minimal with this geometry.

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Fig. 1. Three different Rib Geometry

Fig. 2. Loading and Boundary Conditions

Fig. 3: Axial Stress Distribution

Fig. 4: Radial Stress Distribution

Fig. 5. Interlaminar Shear Stress Distribution

Fig. 6. 5th Mode of Buckling for Rectangular rib

Fig. 7. 5th Mode of Buckling for Taper Rib

Fig. 8. 5th Mode of Buckling for Triangular Rib